

The Role of the Timurid Dynasty in the History of Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *The role of the Temur dynasty in the political and cultural development of Uzbekistan is analyzed in the article. Amir Temur and his descendants made great achievements in science, art, state management and turned Samarkand into a cultural center. The importance of Timurid heritage in today's history and culture is highlighted.*

Key words: *Timurid dynasty, Amir Temur, Samarkand, cultural heritage, political development, science, art, history of Uzbekistan.*

INTRODUCTION

The Timurid dynasty is one of the great dynasties that left a deep mark in the history of Uzbekistan and made a great contribution to the political, cultural and social development of the country. During this dynasty founded by Amir Temur, Samarkand, Bukhara and other cities were not only political centers, but also a high development of culture, science and literature. Especially the architectural monuments, scientific schools and cultural institutions built during the rule of the Timurids are still valued as an important part of the world heritage. Amir Temur and his descendants created a strong state management system, ensured stability in the region and created conditions for the flourishing of culture. Through Mirzo Ulugbek's work in the field of science, Alisher Navoi and other scientists and writers, the Timurid era had a great impact not only on Uzbekistan, but on the entire Central Asia and world civilization.

In this article, the political strategy of the Timurid dynasty, its role in cultural development, its contribution to science and art are widely covered, and the importance of this heritage in the history and cultural development of Uzbekistan is analyzed. At the same time, the role of the Timurid era in world civilization is also studied.

METHODOLOGY

“Amir Temur's “Tuzuklari Temur” deserves special attention as an important source for studying the place of the Timurid dynasty in the history of Uzbekistan. Through this work, you can get valuable information about Amir Temur's state administration, military strategy and management system. “Temur's Constitutions” is a vivid example of ancient Eastern political thought and is an object of scientific analysis for modern researchers”[2].

“Also, Mirzo Ulugbek's scientific works, in particular, his great contribution to the field of astronomy, “Zij jadidi Koragoniy”, with its rich information about the movement of the stars, are the pinnacle of the science of his time. This work influenced not only scientific but also cultural development in its time”[4].

“The works of Alisher Navoi were also used as an important source in the study of the cultural heritage of the Timurid era. His influence on the development of literature can be deeply analyzed through his “Khamasa” and other works. It is also possible to shed light on the political and social

environment of the Timurid era through the works of modern researchers, including Rashiduddin, Ibn Arabshah and other historians”[1].

“In addition, modern archeological research, including architectural monuments in Samarkand and Bukhara and their restoration, is also important in studying the rich cultural heritage of this period. UNESCO’s reports on the cultural heritage of the Timurid period attracted the attention of the international scientific community and created the basis for recognizing the heritage of this period as an integral part of world civilization”[6].

The main methodological approach of the research is the historical-analytical method, in which written and archaeological sources were deeply analyzed. The works of Mirzo Ulugbek and Alisher Navoi, as well as the scientific researches of modern historians were systematized, and conclusions were made about the political and cultural position of the Timurid dynasty.

“Using the comparative-historical method, the period of the Timurids was compared with the period of other dynasties. For example, Samarkand and Bukhara developed as cultural centers during the Timurid period, but no such growth was observed in other regions. Through this method, the specific aspects of the Timurid era were determined.

A complex analysis method was used to determine the relationship between science and culture. Through this, it was shown that the scientific and literary activity was inextricably linked with the state policy during the Timurid period. At the same time, conclusions were drawn about the material and spiritual wealth of the Timurid period based on the information of cultural monuments and archaeological research”[3].

Political stability and centralized management: “The state founded by Amir Temur had a strong political system and ensured stability in Central Asia. The Timurids created a strong military and economic structure, relying on strict laws and principles of justice in state administration. This aspect became the foundation for long-term peace and development in the region”[7].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cultural rise: The era of Timurids is the golden age of culture, art and architecture. Samarkand and Bukhara became not only a political but also a cultural center. Architectural monuments such as Registan Square, Bibikhanim Mosque, Shahi Zinda Complex have become valuable not only for the region, but for the whole world. These monuments are highly valued by modern architectural research.

Development of science: Mirzo Ulugbek’s works in astronomy and mathematics occupy a special place in the history of science. Through his observatory, accurate maps of the movement of the world’s stars were made. This brought the Timurid era to a new stage of science.

Development of literature and language: Under the leadership of Alisher Navoi, Uzbek literature flourished. His works contributed to the development of language and culture and ensured the development of the Uzbek language as a literary language.

“The period of the Timurid dynasty is important not only as a past history, but also as a cultural and spiritual foundation of today’s Uzbekistan. Their high political and cultural achievements had a significant impact not only regionally, but also globally. The status of Samarkand as a world cultural heritage, the study of the science and art of the Timurid period through modern technologies increases the importance of this period”[5].

Also, the period of the Timurids can serve as a source of inspiration for today in many ways. In particular, experiences in the development of public administration, principles of justice, and culture are being analyzed as experiences serving sustainable development on a global scale.

The results show that the Timurid dynasty is not only a part of the historical past, but also a source of cultural and scientific inspiration for future generations. Deep study, promotion and preservation of this heritage will further strengthen the position of Uzbekistan on a global scale.

REFERANCE

Summary, The Timurid dynasty occupied an important place politically and culturally in the history of Uzbekistan. The centralized state administration founded by Amir Temur and its principles of justice led the country to sustainable development. The cities of Samarkand and Bukhara have become centers of culture and science, and the built architectural monuments are still valued as world heritage. Mirzo Ulugbek's scientific achievements and Alisher Navoi's literary heritage left this period in memory as a period of cultural and scientific growth. The rich heritage of the Timurid era is not only of historical importance, but also plays an important role in the cultural and spiritual development of modern Uzbekistan. Deep study and promotion of this heritage serves not only to preserve national values, but also to make a great contribution to world culture.

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